

RDM Infrastructure and Active Data Management

Integration of Data Applications by Interface Design

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Abstract

This paper addresses the problem of incorporating a steadily growing number of research software applications into an existing RDM infrastructure as well as transferring their diverse outputs to the existing storage systems using interface definitions. A sub-process in the general RDM infrastructure is proposed integrating a new software component, the data transfer facilitator (DTF), to facilitate data transfer to a standardized large-scale data repository. Each new research project that implements a research software registers at the DTF and receives an interface endpoint definition. Via this endpoint the DTF monitors any relevant changes to the data model and notifies the administrator if the endpoint definition has to be changed. The need for such a component becomes clear when considering the non-linear interrelationship between the number of tasks of a data curator and the number of research projects to be maintained. Neither is research data scalable at will, nor the curation tasks carried out on them. The main effect of additional (and probably needless) curation work is due to the inefficient transfer of data from the research application, in which data is collected and analyzed, to the data repository, in which the data is archived and made accessible. Formats and standards are rarely met and the timely shifts between the beginning and the end of a project promote information loss. During the time of a project, information on the specifics of the research application and the preparation of research data are seldom documented and, as a consequence, important information is lost towards the end of a project – a time where usually the transfer of data to the archiving infrastructure takes place and for which, the information is indispensable. The DTF remedies this issue by simply treating the endpoint definition as if it was part of the original software that has to be fixed at the time of change.

1 Motivation and Background

Small-scale research projects usually develop idiosyncratic makeshift software solutions suited for the very specific needs of analyzing and viewing data of a particular model and format [1]. This method turns out to be effective for active data management during the time of the project [2]. However, as soon as the end of the project leaps into view and funding runs out, the approach fails to meet the promised data sustainability commitment [3]. Thinking along the lines of the FAIR principles [4], [5]

and the research data lifecycle, on the one hand, as well as considering flexibility and financial means of small research projects, on the other hand, conflicts of objectives are observable. These conflicts often escalate if not addressed appropriately. And they could be solved with the help of information technology if acknowledged in due time [6].

The reports of several qualitative expert interviews and quantitative surveys reveal that small sized projects indeed like to have the advantages of elaborated RDM infrastructures to become more transparent and sustainable [7]. At the same time, they argue rightfully that the transmission of research data from commercial ready-to-use content management systems or their own in-house developments already were problematic either due to export restrictions or a grown impenetrability of distributed data and software [8].

2 Use Case and Component View

The use case in figure 1 differentiates between the role of a project owner (Principal Investigator of a project) and the role of a researcher. Indeed, the depiction includes the possibility that the project owner can also fulfill the role of a researcher. Yet, it must be clear that the project owner has the access rights to the infrastructure for the overall project data. Therefore, it is the credentials of the project owner to which the interface definitions have to be linked. This is the case for both the DMP, in which the attributes of the project's data management plan are kept, and the repository harboring the meta-data as well as the research data. The project owner will also determine the time at which the research data is transferred to the permanent storage infrastructure, which is done via the DTF. The specific endpoint definition is defined by the data curator based on the information received from data modeler who usually is one of the researchers. The role of the researcher is to create the data models and work with the research application, i.e. entering research data or analyzing it. However, the researcher should not interfere with the project owner's scope of responsibility and is therefore not eligible to define access tokens in the repository since it would enable the researcher to change access rights, licenses, or embargoed data for which the project owner is legally held accountable.

The above use case can be translated into a component diagram (figure 2). In this diagram the university infrastructure is assumed to be an abstract component, whose boundaries are arbitrarily set for reasons of conceptual clarity. It includes subsystems such as the institutional data base service, but also a standardized framework for the active data management and other research software projects. The DTF, the data repository and the DMP tool are perceived as self-contained components although they may as well be subsystems of the university infrastructure. The DTF component itself comprises four subsystems, from which the *Formatter* is key. It contains the endpoint definitions and depending on these definitions performs transformations to the agreed standards. The *Formatter* communicates via interfaces with the backends of the research applications, that is, most of the time the central database service or the institutional file store. For some of the idiosyncratic stand-alone applications, it is necessary to access directly to program logic. Moreover, the *Formatter* receives input from the user interface such as a selection of the available data formats, which datasets should be transferred, or the license. The UI also asks the project owner to submit a token that allows access to the personalized area of the data repository. From the DMP component, the *Formatter* may optionally receive meta data of the project under

Figure 1. DTF Use Case

consideration. Finally, the Transfer component handles the actual transmission of the formatted and enriched data to the data repository.

Figure 2. DTF and Infrastructural Services as Components

3 Summary

The new software component, DTF, integrated into a current RDM-architecture, places greater responsibility on the researcher managing the research software throughout the project’s duration. This responsibility includes ensuring that any changes to the structure or storage location of the data are communicated to the data curator. In case of using the supported frameworks, data structure and storage are known and need not be made explicit. The task of the data curator shifts from investigating and restoring deprecated applications and data access to providing and maintaining workable endpoints in the DTF. Time and resources are saved just by rearranging the point in time at which problems occur, i.e. changes are communicated and implemented as if

the research application were part of the design pattern of the DTF and thus part of an overarching software architecture. Really, this is not the case. All makeshift software is still completely independent. Using interfaces, however, a dependence can be simulated without the risk of a system crash in case a subsystem fails, but keeping the advantage that problems are advised to be solved when they occur.

Data Availability Statement

No data is shared in the paper.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Software, Writing – review & editing

Competing interests

The author declares that he has no competing interests.

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